

A Study on Overview of Fast-Moving Consumable Goods (FMCG) Sector in India

AJJAPPA KADUR¹, DR.CHITRA.C.N²

¹Research Scholar, ²Professor and Research Guide

S.S.Patil Research Foundation

B.R.Tambakad First Grade College & PG Studies, Hirekerur haveri (D)-581111, Karnataka

Abstract: Fast-Moving Consumable Goods (FMCG) are essential products to the people to lead a life, such kind of goods are frequently consumed by the people of the society irrespective of their economic status, but consumption capacity is varying based on economic condition of the people. The FMCG sector have a vital role on the economic development of a country, because this sector directly and indirectly influences on the growth of the economy of a country by creation of finance to the government through the collection of tax on production and supply of goods, creation of employment at various levels of this sector, utilization of natural resources and import-export activity. etc, this paper covers the overview of the FMCG Sector.

Keywords: FMCG, ECONOMY, GROWTH, MARKET.

INTRODUCTION

Fast-Moving Consumable Goods (FMCG) that are produced, distributed, marketed, and consumed within a short span of time, this sector dominates the market relates to products such as detergents, electronic products, toiletries, toothpaste, cosmetics, packaged food and beverages, daily usage products. These sectors have a low operating cost easy manufacturing and delivery process, less capital investment, less legal and regulatory process for establishment and high consumer base.

FMCG Industry in India

Fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) sector is India's fourth-largest sector. Consumer-oriented growth and increased prices, particularly for essential products, fueled the growth of the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) industry in India.

- The FMCG sector achieved a milestone of US\$ 56.8 billion by December 2022.
- Forecasts indicate that the total revenue of the FMCG market is expected to experience a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 27.9% from 2021 to 2027, eventually reaching a value of approximately US\$ 615.87 billion.
- In 2022, the urban sector accounted for 65% of the overall annual FMCG sales, while rural India contributed over 35%.
- Household and personal care products make up **50% of the industry's sales**, healthcare claims 31-32%, and food and beverage products account for the remaining 18-19%, which makes it evident that these sectors play a pivotal role in shaping the nation's economic landscape.
- Within this ever-expanding and dynamic industry, the warehouse serves as the beating heart that connects manufacturers, distributors, retailers, and, ultimately, the end consumers, ensuring seamless e-commerce operations.

Review of literature

Prof. MUDASIR AHAMED KHAN N and Prof. AYUB AHAMED K.S (2019): In this study they describe the overview about the FMCG sector relates to growth and impact of the FMCG sector on human life.

Mrs. V. RAJALAKSHMI & Dr.K.UMA DEVI (2020): this study analysis the importance of brand awareness on the new products and consumer opinion on the chemical free products and the price. This study is concluded on the opinion of the different group of customers.

Dr. Pramod H. Patil (2016): This study explained the importance of FMCG sector on economic growth, creation of employment, consumer income, change of customer life style, importance of brand awareness to avoid competition from unorganized sectors.

Dr.V.T. Dhanaraj (2020): In this paper they analyse the importance of brand awareness relating to the FMCG products to the rural customers for protecting the branded products from unbranded products and sustain the products from urban markets to the rural market.

Raghuram.R & Dr.Balasubramania Raja.G: This paper analyses the importance of healthy products and quality of the products by taking an opinion from a specific group of people.

Objectives of the study

1. To understand the concept of FMCG
2. To study the role of FMCG sector on economic development of a country
3. To examine the opportunities and problems of FMCG sector
4. To analyse the role of FMCG for the development of stakeholder

Research Methodology

This study is based on the descriptive nature. For this study the information is collected through the secondary data like relevant literature, research papers, published reports and news articles, journals, internet and web browsers.

Scope of the study

This study is limited to problems, opportunities and challenges, marketing strategies and overview of the FMCG sector.

Conceptual framework

WHAT IS FMCG?

Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG), or Consumer Packaged Goods (CPG), are products sold quickly and at a relatively low cost. The FMCG industry is characterized by high-volume sales, quick inventory turnover, and various products catering to consumer needs.

These goods include essential everyday items such as food and beverages, toiletries, cleaning supplies, and other low-cost household items.

CRITICAL COMPONENTS OF THE FMCG INDUSTRY

Types of FMCG Products

FMCG products can be broadly categorized into three main segments:

- **Food and beverages:** This segment includes packaged foods, snacks, dairy products, carbonated and non-carbonated beverages, and alcoholic drinks.
- **Personal care and toiletries:** This segment comprises cosmetics, soaps, shampoos, skincare items, and oral care products.
- **Household and cleaning items:** This segment covers cleaning supplies, laundry detergents, insecticides, and other essential household items.

Some products that are not classified as fast-moving consumer goods

- Cars and other vehicles
- Clothing
- Books
- Devices such as laptops and mobile phones

Distribution Channels of FMCG Products

Efficient distribution channels are critical to the success of FMCG companies. The most common distribution channels include:

These companies heavily invest in marketing and advertising to boost brand awareness and drive sales. Key marketing strategies include:

- Product packaging and design
- In-store promotions and displays
- Digital and social media marketing
- Influencer partnerships and endorsements
- Sponsorships and event marketing

TOP FMCG COMPANIES AND BRANDS

Some of the world's leading companies and brands in this category include:

1. Procter & Gamble
2. Nestlé
3. Unilever
4. PepsiCo
5. The Coca-Cola Company

These companies have a broad product portfolio that caters to different consumer segments, ensuring a strong market presence and consistent growth.

IMPORTANCE OF FMCG IN THE ECONOMY

The FMCG industry is a vital component of the global economy, contributing significantly to a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and job creation. As a major driver of consumer spending, FMCG plays an essential role in various aspects of the economy, such as the retail and distribution sectors, generating demand for a range of products and services. Here are some of how the FMCG industry contributes to the economy:

1. Economic Growth and Employment

The FMCG sector is a primary source of employment, providing millions of jobs across the supply chain, including manufacturing, distribution, retail, and marketing. As a labor-intensive sector, this industry contributes to economic growth by creating direct and indirect employment opportunities, helping to reduce unemployment rates and boost overall productivity.

2. Driving Retail and Distribution Growth

FMCG products' play a crucial role in the growth of the retail and distribution sectors, generating a steady demand for various products. The high volume and quick turnover encourage retailers and distributors to invest in infrastructure, technology, and workforce development, further supporting economic growth.

3. Tax Revenues for Governments

The FMCG sector generates significant government tax revenues through sales, value-added, and corporate taxes. These revenues are essential for funding public services, infrastructure projects, and social programs, contributing to economic development and stability.

4. Supporting Ancillary Industries

The FMCG industry has strong linkages with various ancillary sectors such as packaging, advertising, logistics, and transportation. The growth and success of these industries are often dependent on the performance of the FMCG sector, creating a multiplier effect on the economy.

KEY TRENDS SHAPING THE FMCG SECTOR

The industry continuously evolves, driven by changing consumer preferences, technological advancements, and economic factors. Some key trends shaping the sector include:

- Growing demand for health and wellness products
- A shift towards eco-friendly packaging and sustainable practices
- Increasing online sales and e-commerce software adoption
- Personalization and customization of products and experiences
- Emphasis on data-driven decision-making and analytics

Opportunities of FMCG Marketing:

- **Higher the population, greater the demands:** The world's population continues to grow, leading to an increase in the number of potential consumers. More people with diverse needs and preferences contribute to the higher demand for FMCG products.
- **Urbanization:** Urbanization is on the rise globally, with more people moving to cities and urban areas. Urban lifestyles often lead to busier schedules, increased disposable income, and a preference for convenient and readily available FMCG products.
- **Changing Consumer Preferences:** Consumer preferences are continually evolving. There is a growing demand for healthier, organic, and sustainable FMCG products, reflecting a shift toward more health-conscious and environmentally-friendly choices.
- **Income Growth:** Rising income levels, especially in emerging economies, have contributed to increased consumer spending on FMCG products. As people's purchasing power increases, they tend to spend more on convenience goods and non-essential items.
- **Convenience and Time Constraints:** FMCG products are designed for convenience and quick consumption. In today's fast-paced world, consumers prefer products that save time and effort, making FMCG goods more attractive.
- **Marketing and Branding:** Effective marketing and branding campaigns by FMCG companies have significantly influenced consumer behavior.
- **Globalization and Trade:** Improved transportation and trade agreements have facilitated the global distribution of FMCG products. Companies can now reach new markets more efficiently, expanding their customer base.
- **Online Retailing:** The growth of e-commerce and online retail platforms has made FMCG products easily accessible to a broader audience. Online shopping provides convenience and opens new markets for FMCG companies.

- **Product Innovation:** The consumer companies in India are continuously introducing new products and variants to cater to changing consumer tastes and preferences.

Major Challenges of FMCG Marketing

- **Intense Competition:**

Due to the large number of customers in the FMCG market, many companies are attracted to it. This has made the market very competitive. It takes a lot of creativity and smart thinking to succeed in this busy market.

- **Customer Attraction:**

When there are so many options in the market, it can be difficult for a brand to get people to notice, especially if they do not already have a lot of loyal customers. To stand out, brands need to have good marketing that speaks to the people they want to sell to.

- **Loyalty Struggles:**

FMCG products are often seen as basic goods that are like each other. This makes it hard for companies to keep customers loyal to them. People in this category often choose products based on the low price, sales, and special deals.

- **Regional Considerations:**

While many FMCG companies operate globally or nationally, achieving success in this industry relies on comprehending and accommodating regional disparities and preferences. Adjusting strategies to local markets is crucial for sustained growth.

Even though FMCG products have a few challenges, a good marketing strategy can alleviate all these and help companies succeed.

- **Limited Storage Space**

One of the primary challenges faced by these brands is the constraint of limited storage space in warehouses. With an ever-expanding product range and increasing consumer demands, finding sufficient space to store inventory becomes a critical concern. Inadequate storage capacity can lead to overcrowding, disorganized stock, and inefficient picking and packing processes. Also, it restricts the ability to maintain optimum stock levels, resulting in stock outs or overstock situations.

- **Seasonality and Demand Variability**

FMCG brands often face fluctuating demand due to seasonal variations and ever-changing consumer preferences. This poses a significant challenge when it comes to forecasting and managing inventory levels. During peak seasons, brands must ensure they have enough stock to meet the heightened demand while avoiding excessive inventory that may lead to waste and additional storage costs.

- **Product Shelf Life and Fragility**

Many FMCG products, particularly perishable goods, and fragile items, have limited shelf life or are sensitive to handling and storage conditions. Maintaining product quality and reducing waste are essential for businesses. Inadequate temperature control, improper handling, and suboptimal packaging can result in spoilage, damage, or expiration of goods.

- **Regulatory Compliance and Quality Control**

FMCG brands operate in a highly regulated environment, subject to various industry standards, safety regulations, and quality control measures. Compliance with these regulations is crucial for maintaining consumer trust and avoiding legal consequences. For example, brands selling food products must effectively manage product expiry dates to ensure consumer safety and satisfaction.

Solution to Challenges in the FMCG Industry

- **Efficient Stock Control and Optimization**

Maintaining accurate inventory levels is important for FMCG companies. A robust warehouse management system (WMS) uses advanced technologies such as barcode scanning at batch, SKU (Stock Keeping Unit), and item levels to monitor inventory levels accurately.

➤ **Space Utilization and Layout Planning**

Efficient space utilization within the warehouse is very important for FMCG brands, as they often deal with a large volume of products. Warehouse management systems help optimize the allocation of space by providing features like shelf management.

This feature enables brands to strategically organize products and implement efficient storage techniques. By doing so, e-commerce businesses can maximize their storage capacity, minimize waste, and streamline their picking and packing processes.

➤ **Quality Control Measures for Ensured Excellence**

The satisfaction of customers is closely tied to the quality of a product. To achieve excellence, a robust WMS incorporates several quality control measures such as cycle counting, expiry management, batch management, and more. Cycle counting involves periodic inventory level checks to identify discrepancies. Expiry management is another critical aspect of warehouse management that prevents selling expired goods, monitoring dates, and following the FIFO or FEFO approach.

With sophisticated WMS using batch management, brands can identify which goods are suitable for sending to B2B (retail stores) and which are more suitable for marketplaces or direct-to-consumer (D2C) channels. For example, B2B retailers need products with 70%+ shelf life, while D2C customers accept shorter shelf life (30-40%) for quick consumption. By sorting products into batches, brands send appropriate batches to each channel.

➤ **Order Fulfillment with Precision and Speed**

FMCG products are typically everyday items consumers rely on for daily needs. Timely and accurate order fulfillment ensures that customers receive their desired products. With the help of optimized picking strategies and strategic product bundling, companies can minimize the time and effort required to locate and retrieve products.

➤ **Efficient Handling of Returns and Refunds**

Efficient handling of returns and refunds is a critical aspect for e-commerce businesses, especially when it comes to FMCGs brands. These businesses understand the importance of prioritizing product quality and safety, which should be reflected in their return policies.

Strategies for FMCG Marketing activities

- Sales through the brand website
- Display of market places
- Utilization of social media strategy
- Sell with pricing and offers
- Customer oriented marketing
- Aggressive advertisement

Findings

1. FMCG sector have a vital role in the growth of the economy of a country
2. It helps to create employment opportunity
3. FMCG sector not effectively reach the rural market
4. It faces many problems from the un-branding products and un-organized institutions
5. FMCG brands faces the demand fluctuation due to seasonal variation
6. This sector face problems of regional disparities
7. This sector face the problems of maintaining customer loyalty
8. This sector faces a major challenge in respect of regulatory decisions to supply of product in nature of eco-friendly, safety measures, quality control, maintaining brand and pricing decision

Suggestions

1. **Partnership and Collaboration**

Collaborating with healthcare professionals, non-profit organizations, and government agencies can help FMCG companies develop and implement effective public health initiatives. These partnerships can include awareness campaigns, nutrition education programs, and support for community health initiatives.

2. **Reducing Harmful Ingredients**

Phasing out or reducing the use of ingredients linked to health issues, such as artificial additives or trans fats, demonstrates a commitment to consumer well-being. FMCG companies should invest in research and development to find healthier alternatives.

3. **Portion Control and Serving Size**

Offering smaller portion sizes and clear guidelines on recommended servings can help consumers make healthier choices. These strategies can help combat overconsumption, a significant factor in rising obesity rates.

4. **Accessibility and Affordability**

Making healthier products affordable and accessible to a broader range of consumers can be a game-changer. Pricing strategies, subsidies, and distribution networks can be used to ensure that healthy choices are within reach for all.

Conclusion

The FMCG sector is essential to the country for its development, economic growth, maintenance of standard of living; in modern days without this sector it is difficult to development of the people and the country. This sector faced many challenges at various levels. Good marketing strategies, utilization of modern marketing tools and techniques & technology will help this sector to overcome from competition of un-branding and un-organized institutions. The aggressive advertisement and sales promotional activities may helpful for cover the rural and regional market.

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